

Characteristics of "Rivers" in the Material Life of Residents in Mekong River Delta, Vietnam

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 19, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: June 25, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Material Life, Vietnamese cultur, national traditional</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5032517</p>	<p><i>Located in the geographical space of Vietnamese culture, the culture of the Mekong River Delta has both expressed unity with the national traditional culture and created its own cultural identity. The environment and natural conditions of the Mekong Delta have added to the national culture its unique feature - the characteristic "river". The article contributes to clarifying the "river" characteristics in the material life of the residents of the Mekong Delta and is related to the context that this land is facing challenges from climate change as well as resource exploitation activities in Mekong River Delta region is unsustainable at present and in the future.</i></p>

Introduction

The Mekong Delta is a low delta region, shaped like a peninsula, subject to the accretion of the Mekong River, nowhere in Vietnam has the number of rivers and canals as many as here. According to statistics, this area has about 54,000km of rivers and canals in length (Dieu, 2014, p. 27). It can be said that the distinctive feature of the Mekong Delta is the "river" characteristic, which is strongly reflected in material life from wet rice agriculture, commercial activities, exploitation and aquaculture to house construction, transportation and food culture.

The article affirms that the economic and cultural values, stability and development of the Mekong Delta in the past and at the present have contributed significantly to the "river" characteristic. Today, climate change and the unsustainable exploitation of water resources by humans are two major challenges, threatening many aspects of people's lives in the Mekong Delta. From the above assessment, the article makes a number of recommendations, which emphasize the issue of raising community awareness and promoting regional linkages so that the "river" characteristics of this land can be preserved. This meets the goals and sustainable development orientation of the Mekong Delta in particular and Vietnam in general.

Literature Review

The Mekong Delta has been used in scientific literature and documents since the Second World War up to now, meaning a large delta located along the lower Mekong region in the west. South of Vietnam (Duong, 1991, p.11-12).

Referring to the Mekong Delta, people think of the image of a floating body of water, as described very nicely by journalist and writer Phan Quang in the book *Mekong Delta*: "Only water reigns in this water and trees... water floats, floating tree, villagers and houses seem to have emerged as well" (Dieu, 2014, p. 24). From Phan Quang's perspective, it can be seen that the "rivers" characteristics of the Mekong Delta penetrate deep into each blood vessel of this land. Within the scope of a scientific article, the writer only studies the "rivers" feature in terms of material life.

The characteristics of "rivers" in the Mekong Delta are clearly reflected in the agricultural and commercial economy of this land. Nguyen Cong Binh, Le Xuan Diem, Mac Duong in the work *Culture and residents of the Mekong Delta* talked about the growth of the heavenly rice variety (Binh, Diem, Duong, 1990, p.258), floating markets, and daily life. love you on boats and boats along the Mekong.

Research on the Mekong Delta cannot fail to mention the "farming" civilization. "The Southern School" Son Nam in the work *Cuu Long Delta - An ancient and civilized life in the garden* said that the garden represents the highest form of material and spiritual life in the Mekong Delta (Nam, 2014, p.242). The open space of garden culture has contributed to creating the liberal character of the people of the South. This character has been

indirectly expressed through the custom of building houses, culinary culture, costumes, etc. of the residents of the Mekong Delta.

In *Cultural Characteristics of the Mekong Delta* showed the relationship between the characteristic of "rivers" and typical features in personality, in cultural and culinary life, festivals, customs and traditions of this land. As he commented on the culinary culture here: "Eating in the Mekong Delta is eating its whole space" (Dieu, 2014, p.88).

In addition to the above studies, the article also has references to other works such as *The Lower Mekong: Challenge to cooperation in Southeast Asia* (Schaaf and Fifield, 1963), *20 Years of Cooperation* (MRC, 2016), *Swamp: National and natural tectonics in the Mekong Delta* (Biggs, 2019)... These works provide documents on the changes of the Mekong Delta before the influence of external factors. Those are the policies of the French colonial government in the twentieth century and the impacts of climate change on this land in the first decades of the twenty-first century.

The above studies have provided the article with an overview of the Mekong Delta, from the historical process of formation and development to aspects in socio-cultural life. The feature of "rivers" is identified and clarified by the writer through his research paper. From the research results, the article believes that for the Mekong Delta region to have sustainable development, the factor "rivers" plays a very important role. In the face of complicated developments of climate change, this needs to be fully and thoroughly understood so that people, local authorities and the State need synchronous and timely solutions.

Research Method

Method and Data

Researching on the characteristics of "rivers" of the Mekong Delta, the writer also relies on the theory of cultural specificity to perceive the distinctiveness of this land. The theory of cultural specificity wants to emphasize and promote the unique identity of each culture. On the basis of this theory, the writer is aware of the "rivers" feature in the cultural life of the Mekong Delta and the importance of preserving and preserving this feature.

With this topic, the writer has applied the main research methods which are historical method, logical method and case study method. The historical method allows to clarify the changes of the "rivers" characteristics of the Mekong Delta over the periods. The logical method helps to identify the nature and characteristics of "rivers" through the economic and daily life of the inhabitants of this land. The writer applies the case study method to clarify the characteristics of "rivers" in daily life in terms of culinary culture, architecture, means of transport; in economic life through images of rice varieties, floating markets... in the Mekong Delta.

Based on the theory of dialectical materialism and historical materialism of the Marxism-Leninism, the article uses specific methods: method analysis, synthesis, methods of data collection and processing. At the same time, there is inheriting research results related to the topic of the article

Results and Discussion

The Mekong Delta consists of 13 provinces and cities: Can Tho, Long An, Tien Giang, Ben Tre, Dong Thap, Vinh Long, Tra Vinh, Hau Giang, An Giang, Soc Trang, Kien Giang, Bac Lieu and Ca Mau. The natural area of the region is about 4 million hectares (accounting for about 12% of the country's area) and the population is over 18 million people (Hiep, 2015). The Mekong Delta has a particularly important position in socio-economic development, ensuring national defense and security. In the historical process, the characteristic of "rivers" is the source of prosperity, creating the distinctiveness of the Mekong Delta, which is expressed through the economic and daily life of the inhabitants of this region.

1. Characteristics of "river" in the economic life of Mekong Delta residents

Agriculture. As a flat land, receiving accretion from the Mekong River with an annual flood regime, wet rice farming is the most effective use of regional resources. Therefore, the history of exploiting the Mekong Delta is associated with the birth and development of wet rice farming.

In the seventeenth century, with the arrival of Vietnamese immigrants - the long-standing owners of wet rice civilization, it brought about a great change in wet rice farming techniques in the Southwest region. With the experience of water treatment, embankment, canal digging, techniques to increase crops, crop support... have existed for thousands of generations, plus the special privileges from the nature of the Mekong Delta, has made wet rice farming make significant progress in productivity. In the past, the inhabitants of the area, completely dependent on the water of the sky, that is, the rainy months of the year, to cultivate the crops. When Vietnamese and then Chinese immigrants came to exploit this area, they applied many different farming methods and techniques, flexibly depending on the objective reality of the ecological regions of the Mekong Delta. In particular, the freshwater alluvial land along and between the Tien river and Hau river are considered the best arable land, most suitable for rice.

The Dong Thap Muoi region is a symbol of the harsh land, proving the bravery of natural conquest of the Vietnamese residents. This is a flooded land, standing water for a long time when the water of the Mekong

River rises in the rainy season, in the dry season, fresh water is scarce. Therefore, the most typical plants for this area are flood-tolerant and acid-tolerant plants such as melaleuca, cajeput, strabismus, water lily... I don't know if that's the case, as to compensate, Mother Nature has bestowed it here is a typical rice variety - heavenly rice, also known as ghost rice. When the rainy season begins, rice is mixed with dense vegetation. Stems are hard, leaves are large, so at first it is difficult to distinguish from weeds. In August, when the flood water is high, it is also the time when ghost rice shows its strong vitality, leaving other grasses to rise; by December, when the flood recedes, people can harvest rice. "The rice grain is small, has a pointed tip, has a long beard, is easy to fall, and usually falls until it ripens. People call the heavenly rice "ghost rice" because it "rips off" and "falls off" at night. At night, people use boats to thresh rice by sitting on the boat, throwing rice plants into the canoe, and the rice falling into the boat(Binh, Diem, & Duong, 1990, p.258). The ghost rice plant in the Dong Thap Muoi region has gone through the entire history of the nation, from the footsteps of the ancestors, to the meals of soldiers in two long resistance wars against the French and against the US. Today, the shadow of this legendary rice variety remains only in Tram Chim National Park. Conservation of this rice variety is not only a cultural-historical issue, but also meets the requirements of the Mekong Delta in the new context.

Back in the seventeenth century, when the Vietnamese settled in the Mekong Delta, they crossed short-stemmed rice from northern Vietnam and China with the wild rice variety (Kiem, 1992, p.53). This has created a variety of rice varieties, adaptability, and length of crops. A French researcher counted more than 500 varieties of rice, including 18 varieties of floating rice in the Mekong Delta in 1900 (Biggs, 2019, p.108). When the canal system does not work in the deeply flooded areas in the rainy season, floating rice varieties open a way out for this field. This rice variety has been tested in the South since 1895, starting from Nang Gu, now in An Giang province (Quang, 2014, p.138). The feature of the floating rice plant is its long stem and is grown in the upper delta where the water is flooded for many months of the year. "Rice plants can grow 10cm long per day, stems can be from 3m to 5m long" (Binh, Diem & Duong, 1990, p.273). Although little care is required, but the yield is low, so today the area of floating rice has narrowed. An Giang is a rare locality in the Mekong Delta that still maintains this rice variety. However, floating rice is currently attracting special attention in today's complex climate change conditions.

It would be a mistake to study the Mekong Delta without mentioning the "hardworking" civilization. "The Southern School" defined by Son Nam: "Mien garden, generally referred to as highland areas, with citrus groves along the banks of the Tien and Hau rivers, in the provinces of Sa Dec, Vinh Long, My Tho, Can Tho, etc. The garden represents the highest form of material and spiritual life in the Mekong Delta" (Nam, 2014, p.242). Although it is only a small area in the overall Mekong Delta, but this place has special incentives from nature such as: the high land is not flooded in the rainy season but still has new alluvium, less alkaline soil, enough fresh water for irrigation and daily living... Therefore, "gardening" is very suitable for the development of orchards, as well as crops.

Commercial. The first impression of visitors to the Mekong Delta must be the interlaced system of canals. As commented by Phan Quang: "The Mekong Delta is really a spider web of rivers and canals. Even local people sometimes cannot distinguish between a canal and a natural canal" (Quang, 2014, p.103). This is necessary for the natural conquest of man in the marshland. Following in the footsteps of the forebears who opened the realm, opened and widened the canals not only helped to expand the rice area, but also profoundly changed the commercial economy of the region.

Bearing similarities with civilizations formed in history, Mekong Delta society is also shaped in riverside areas and along canals. In a large delta area, with many natural rivers and canals, flooded for several months, water transport is almost unique in the Mekong Delta. "The houses are close to the canal bank, overlooking the river. The same goes for wholesalers and craft houses. Visitors visit the boat to trade and transact; goods come and go by water. Places bordering water, or at junctions, road intersections, densely populated, gradually having shops, markets, towns, becoming larger, becoming administrative or commercial centers, on wharfs under boats" (Quang, 2014, p. 74).

If the role of the Vietnamese in developing wet rice farming techniques in the Mekong Delta is undeniable, in the commercial sector, the Chinese have soon affirmed their number one role. This has both objective and subjective reasons. In the seventeenth century, the commodity economy of the South was still very weak, which was inevitable in a feudal society with the view of "respecting farmers and trades". For the Chinese who have left behind their homeland, ancestors, clans... to find a livelihood in a faraway land, the view of the social ladder does not make much sense. The weak gap of southern trade was fully utilized by the Chinese, many of whom rose to become big merchants like in the case of Chu Hoa, Quach Dam...

With an extensive network of rivers and canals in the Southwest, there are large rivers overflowing the banks, the water is clear, and there are boats and boats that live day and night on the river. Because of that, this place has produced a typical culture of the river region, which is the floating market. The floating market is open all day, but it is most crowded in the morning, when it is still foggy, the wind is cool and the sun is still mild. When the sun is high, the sun begins to be strong, the market is crowded and the boats and boats are less and less crowded. The unique feature of floating markets compared to terrestrial markets is that trade is carried out in the

form of "cheetah". Sellers often put poles in front of their boats and symbolically hang the items they are selling. This form of "leopard goods" is a unique trading culture found only in floating markets, which is not noisy and bustling but enough to attract attention. Today, in addition to the traditional "soldier" form, sellers also know how to promote their goods in more modern methods such as using signs, banners, light boxes... Traders on floating markets meeting by boat. In the past, there were three-leaf canoe, five-leaf boat, and three-leaf boat. Now there are switches and motorboats. Buyers also come to the market by canoe or boat. The small boats skillfully weave between hundreds of boats and boats without any collisions. Although meeting on the river, the floating market has almost no shortage of any item, from fruit to seafood, poultry, even cloth, shoes, needles... Even bars are held on the river. You can find here rustic Southern dishes such as tet cake, coconut leaf sticky rice cake, orange cake, tofu, puff pastry, sweet soup cake, filter cake, garden noodle... Most provinces and regions The West has this form of market, but the most diverse in goods are the markets: Cai Rang market (Can Tho), Cai Be market (Tien Giang), Phung Hiep market (Hau Giang) and Long Xuyen floating market. . Currently, localities in the Mekong Delta are creating strength in exploiting floating markets, making them attractive tourist attractions - a typical cultural feature of the key economic region of the Southwest region. For many years, visiting the floating market has become an attractive tourist route for tourists from near and far. Therefore, the preservation and development of the cultural and tourist functions of the floating market should be given due attention. Managing, channeling, dividing lots as well as building a new and modern cultural lifestyle of the floating market is posing a task in the period of innovation, industrialization and modernization for the Mekong Delta localities.

2. Characteristics of "river" in the daily life of Mekong Delta residents

House. The model of a house commonly seen in the Mekong Delta is facing the canal or river, the back is a garden, the back of the garden is a field. At the river wharf in front of the house, people often take a wooden plank bridge, sometimes just a coconut tree or two, to go to the river to make a place to wash, bathe, wash dishes... Next to the bridge, people often store it thatched roofs make a place for boats and canoes to park to avoid sun and rain. Along the riverside are rows of crazy books, chopsticks, cork, coconut... With basic functions, suitable for the river area, if you don't have the need to go far, get rich, just hang around in front of the river after the fields around. At home, the basic needs of life can also be temporarily met. In addition, to adapt to the lowlands, which are flooded all year round, people in low-lying areas build temporary houses to adapt to the natural conditions of the area.

In a land where "the birds are scared, the fish are scared", people live dependent on each other in residential clusters, often without clear boundaries between this village, that village, between house and house. It's also just a conventional fence like hibiscus, ornamental tea, mandarin oranges... Community cohesion is strongly embedded in the lifestyles of Vietnamese, Khmer and Cham people; for the Chinese, they are more mobile. This also comes from the characteristics of their main occupation, which is trading. Depending on each ethnic group, there are different ways to build and decorate houses. However, in general, the ethnic groups in the Mekong Delta are similar in the materials used (wood, bamboo, nipa leaves...), with a rustic, simple style, living in harmony, close to nature.

Today, along with the process of urbanization, the characteristics of the house architecture of the people of the Southwest region are also much different from the past. In addition, in the flooded area, residents have used new construction materials to be suitable, convenient and safe for life.

Traffic. With an area of canals interlaced like spider webs, waterway traffic plays a vital role in the Mekong Delta. In the last decades of the 18th century, the Dang Trong government developed a system of canals in this region such as Vung Cu canal (ie Bao Dinh canal), Thuong Mai canal, Rut Ngua canal... The canal system brought "a great benefit to the people" (Cuong, 2017, p.148). In the 19th century, under the Nguyen Dynasty, the court developed a system of canals in the area bordering Vietnam and Cambodia. Two big projects at that time were Thoai Ha canal and Vinh Te canal. Although designed by political requirements to protect the delta from the Siamese expansionist plot, the southern canal system made contributions to the development of Vietnamese commerce at that time.

From the end of the 19th century, after mastering the entire Indochina region, the French colonialists paid great attention to developing the waterway transportation system. The Mekong River flows along the Indochina colonies from North to South and is the main freight route in the region. Since 1866, the French colonialists have dredged to expand the system of canals in the Mekong Delta to serve agricultural production and navigation in the Lower Mekong Delta. In 1893, about 180,000 m³ of mud was dredged. This number increased from 8 to 13 million m³ annually between 1913-1930. In 1937 alone, about 2,700,000 m³ of land was dredged in the Mekong Delta. In addition, during the period 1905-1935, France also built concrete landmarks to mark dangerous locations on the Mekong River, especially on the waterway to Luang Prabang. Channels with low or medium water levels are also improved by blasting or removing blocking rocks (Schaaf & Fifield, 1963, p.81). These works, when completed, have created a very convenient waterway transportation system connecting the Mekong Delta region to Phnom Penh and a number of other provinces in Cambodia and Laos.

It is difficult to remember the exact length of the canals, as well as the types of waterway transport in this land. The people of the Mekong Delta, in the process of land reclamation, have deeply felt the natural features of this place to create boats, not only a means of transportation but also a means of livelihood.

Each type of boat and boat has different functions. To transport goods, people build large boats with heavy carrying capacity that can travel long distances; Depending on different types of goods, used are types of boats such as: gourd boat, door boat, cage boat, truss boat, beige boat, fishing boat, row boat, fishing boat, basket boat, raft boat. In the case of fast moving and light transportation, people use boats: net boats, shrimp rake boats. In addition, in each locality, people build their own boats suitable for river conditions and production and travel needs in the region, such as Phu Quoc fishing boat, Ba Ria vibrating net boat, Cua Ba boat. Ria, Phuoc Hai fishing boat, Can Duoc boat... In the case of traveling in ditches, swamps, fields, people use small, compact boats, canoes, which are also very diverse such as basket boats, canoes. three-leaf, three-banner, tac gong. These are the most common, most popular and most maneuverable vehicles. Along with the development of the residential community, there were boats and boats dedicated to public services, the needs of the well-to-do class, and even military activities. Typically, the Hau boat is a rather luxurious boat, for the governor, the tri government, and the district; a boat with a hood from the tip of the nose to the end of the boat, used to carry soldiers; the boat has a roof that is painted with gilded vermilion, with a smooth board lining inside to serve as a place to cook, eat, and smoke opium, often used for the rich, landlords use to travel, eat, visit... (Binh, Diem & Duong, p.322-325).

With such a large number and variety of boats, people in the Mekong Delta had a convention of traveling on the river from the very beginning. Trinh Hoai Duc in *Gia Dinh Thanh Thong Chi* wrote: "Regardless of whether the boat or boat encounters favorable or unfavorable wind and water, when approaching each other, they must shout "bow", then their boat must go to the right, the other boat also follows the side. possession, so that they can control and avoid each other" (Binh, Diem & Duong, p. 325-326).

Along with the development of the country, the waterway means of transport in the Mekong Delta appear popular with some new and modern types such as motorboats, canoes... However, the above-mentioned traditional means, although some are not are still in use or have changed in function, but most of them still retain their role in the Mekong Delta.

In addition to boats, in rivers that are not convenient to use dinghy, Westerners often catch simple bridges for easy travel. The body of the bridge is usually made of bamboo or wood lying on crossed bamboo slats, above there are handrails, called monkey bridge. This is an unmistakable unique culture of the Mekong Delta. The loose bridge has added beauty to the village when the roads are separated by rivers and canals. The water is shallow, the canal is small, the body of the monkey bridge is neatly connected here and there by a few bamboo tops, five or three trees, cork, areca trees, coconut trees, a bunch of forest rattan ropes, the rope is a monkey bridge. was present on the side of life in the countryside of the river, connecting the two banks for people to go back and forth, every day like every other day, bringing joy and happiness to the village canals. Today, in modern life, the monkey bridge in the Mekong Delta is gradually replaced by stronger and wider cement and plank bridges. Monkey bridge only exists in the villages, isles and gardens of the West, but it is forever imprinted in the memory of the people of the Southwest region as a very unique beauty of the landscape and daily life. of people in the Mekong Delta.

Culinary culture. With the incentives given by nature - a system of rivers and canals interlaced with seasonal fluctuating flow regimes, on a mild climate, has created a diverse ecosystem for the land here. Therefore, the culinary culture in the region is also very rich and unique.

With an abundant source of rice, rice is the main food in family meals in the Mekong Delta. In addition, from rice seeds, people also know how to grind into flour to make many kinds of cakes, famous as silkworm cake, little cake, banh xeo, banh ask, banh khot... Not only diverse in rice varieties, the Mekong Delta is also famous. with cereals and vegetables. In which, it must be mentioned the types whose names have brought the culinary characteristics of the region such as cotton sop, crazy cotton... With the characteristic of being a plant that grows naturally without human care, coconut has a lot in the Mekong Delta, so not only popularly used to make houses, people here have the habit of using coconut in food processing. This is also a unique feature in the cuisine of the Southwest region.

Being a multi-ecological region, with many rivers and canals, mangroves, grasslands, swamps and sea, the aquatic resources of the Mekong Delta are very rich: shrimp, fish, crabs, turtles, snakes, snails, clams, oysters, clams, mussels, eels... in which, each species has a diversity of species. This is an important material to build a culinary culture of the Southwest region. Among the popular and unique dishes of the Mekong Delta, the first thing to mention is fish sauce. The fish sauce here is very diverse because it is made from many types of seafood and different processing methods, so the products made are also very diverse in color and taste. "The Khmer people have different kinds of fish sauce such as sauce prahoc, lao le sauce, on pu, and poliong sauce. The Cham people have salac sauce, genen fish sauce, calok sauce, half pau fish sauce, bu Van fish sauce, pa fish sauce, and sharp fish sauce. As for the Vietnamese, there are dozens of types of fish sauce. Each region has its own kind of fish sauce..." (Binh, Diem & Duong, p. 343).

When it comes to the culinary culture of the Mekong Delta, it is not only about the unique features of the dishes, but more importantly, reflecting the soul and personality of the people here. In the early days of reclaiming and establishing a business, people could not help but be afraid and amazed at the wild grassy land and raging wild animals. Therefore, in order to survive, they cannot avoid but face and conquer with nature. Wild personality, enterprising not only in human temperament but also began to take shape in Southern culinary culture since that day. This is shown very clearly through the use of wild plants and animals, from bitter vegetables, cotton bud, tickle ... to crabs, crabs, rat, toads, frogs, le le, etc. bats, locusts, scorpions, crickets... The culinary space of the Mekong Delta cannot be set outside the context of the river here. Son Nam wrote: "On a cool, windy moon night, many people who like arts and arts organize boat trips on the Tien or Hau rivers, thinking that they are Mr. To Dong Pha and his friends walking on the Xich Bich River, in a moment it turns out. first, spread wings to fly high. The cruise took the dan ca, reciting poetry, painting, and eating as important things: playing art, eating shrimp grilled over embers, reciting bowls of owls, talking jokes until the moon set. This hobby is called freeing the birds" (Nam, 2014, p. 341). Putting food in its space can fully see the country soul, the cultural depth hidden in it. The Mekong Delta is probably a typical example.

With the nature of a multi-ethnic land, the culinary culture of the Mekong Delta is also integrated at an early age. With the nature of the subject ethnic group, the Vietnamese have a great influence on the culinary culture of the region. This shows the savory braised dishes in daily meals, the variety of cakes, especially banh tet on Tet. However, in the process of coexistence, the ethnic groups had cultural interference and acclimatization with each other. The Vietnamese used a number of traditional Khmer items such as the "ca rang" (kind of stove), ceramic pot to store anchovies, and "braised" water jugs. Some traditional dishes of the Khmer are adapted by the Vietnamese to suit their taste, such as sour soup, vermicelli in Bac Lieu, etc. The Cham people also popularize Muslim curries in Southern cuisine. Hot pot dishes, fried noodles, fried rice... are traditional dishes of the Chinese people are also welcomed by ethnic communities in the Southwest region. The culinary culture of the Mekong Delta can be considered in many other characteristics such as creativity, balance... but perhaps along with the "rivers" characteristics, wildness, space, and integration are the hallmarks in terms of culinary culture of this river region.

3. Some challenges in the material life of the Mekong Delta residents at present and in the future

As a lowland area, accreted from alluvium of the Mekong River, the Mekong Delta is facing challenges due to impacts from nature and humans. In recent years, climate change has made natural disasters here complicated and unpredictable, causing damage to people and property. But the most worrying thing is an existing risk of water security, food security as well as social issues such as people's livelihood here. In the report of the United Nations Development Program released in 2007, the countries in the Lower Mekong region are among the regions most severely affected by climate change. In particular, the Mekong Delta region is the most vulnerable to sea level rise due to the impact of climate change. Tran Kien Mai, a climate change expert at the MRC, said that without practical solutions, sea levels will rise by 0.8 m to 1 m by 2100, in which case 38% of the Mekong Delta will be hit sinking, about 30% of the region's population will be affected and many will be forced to migrate (MRC, 2016, p.35).

In recent decades, the Mekong Delta has been experiencing strong impacts of climate change. Historically, this land has rarely experienced serious disasters. However, for 3 consecutive years from 2000-2002, there were major floods in the area, in which there were historical big floods in 2000; Two big storms named Linda (1997) and Durian (2006) suddenly landed in the Mekong Delta, causing the people of the land, who did not have much experience in flood and storm control, to suffer great losses of people and lives. In addition, the shortage of water sources aggravates the problem of saline soil and riverside erosion... causing serious consequences, threatening the development of the whole region.

In addition to the effects of climate change, the Mekong Delta is facing many challenges caused by humans. The rapid economic development but not paying attention to sustainable development, along with the constant increase in population has seriously affected the quality of water resources. The increase in forms of intensive farming, increased crops in rice production, aquaculture, and livestock raising... causes water sources to be contaminated with residues of agricultural drugs, herbicides, pesticides, antibiotics, etc. weight gainers, undissolved organic substances. The custom of building houses and meeting markets right on rivers and canals causes water sources to receive many sources of waste in daily life. In addition, with the economic restructuring in the direction of developing industry groups - services, many industrial parks, export processing zones, factories, entertainment centers were born, along the river, Untreated industrial wastewater has the opportunity to overflow into canals and rivers, limiting the ability to self-clean natural water sources. These are the main reasons leading to the deterioration of the quality of surface water as well as groundwater in the Mekong Delta, and pollution in many places has reached an alarming level.

As an international river, the strategy of countries in the Mekong River region towards river exploitation has a direct impact on Vietnam in general and the Mekong Delta in particular. The most worrying issue now is that China has operated and continues to promote the construction of hydropower dams on the mainstream. Laos - a downstream country has also implemented a series of hydropower projects with the ambition of becoming a

"battery battery" in the region. Many organizations, research institutes, research centers, universities of regional and international countries have carried out a series of research projects related to this issue. The worrying thing is that all the reports share the same opinion about the possibility that if the Mekong were to be crushed by dams on both mainstream and tributaries, it would be an unpredictable disaster on many fronts, not just the socio-economic losses that may even lead to political conflicts between countries in the region. The problem here is to be aware of and assess the challenges in the new context, in order to quickly find a way to overcome the immediate difficulties, and at the same time to have a long-term vision, a long-term strategy and a long-term strategy. with specific action plans to proactively respond and adapt.

4. A few recommendations

The history of formation and development of the Mekong Delta is associated with the continuous accumulation of the Mekong River. The international nature of the river has brought about the international character of the region, along with the "rivers" characteristic, which has profoundly influenced and influenced the development of the Mekong Delta throughout the historical process. Today, in the face of the complex effects of climate change, the urgent requirement is to quickly find a system of current solutions along with a long-term orientation so that the region can continue to promote the strengths of climate change. preserving traditional cultural values, contributing to building a rich, beautiful and sustainable Vietnamese culture. On the basis of consulting opinions and opinions of leaders, researchers and scholars in related topics, the article emphasizes the importance of the following issues:

Firstly, raising awareness of people in the Mekong Delta about the challenge and adaptation to climate change. Currently, the Mekong Delta has implemented projects to raise public awareness on climate change. Most of the projects are supported by development partners and international organizations. However, it is important that projects need to be replicated, deployed, synchronously in localities, must be inherited, continuous and long-term to bring sustainable effects.

Secondly, building effective and close cooperation relations with countries in the Mekong River basin in the issue of effective and sustainable exploitation of water resources of the Mekong River.

Thirdly, synchronously develop the system of urban centers, residential areas and the system of technical and social infrastructure in the direction of being eco-friendly in association with fields, gardens, rivers and Sea Island.

Fourthly, sustainable development, linking socio-economic development with economical use of resources, protection of the ecological environment; take proactive measures to prevent and respond to climate change and sea level rise; closely combine socio-economic development with assurance of national defense and security, water source security and food security.

Fifthly, an overall approach of inter-regional and inter-sectoral nature in socio-economic development of the whole Mekong Delta region, forming a synchronous coordination mechanism horizontally between localities and vertically between agencies Central and local.

Conclusion

From the study of the "rivers" characteristics in the material life of the residents of the Mekong Delta, they are more and more aware of the role of the Mekong River in the socio-economic development of the region. The water source of the Mekong River is the source of the agricultural and commercial development of this land. In social relations, the river not only provides a source of water with the meaning of ensuring quality and quantity, creating livelihoods for people on both sides of the basin, making an important contribution to the development of the region is a bridge connecting countries in the region in the cultural space of Mekong. Recognizing the role of the river in order to have the right behavior in exploiting and sharing resources from the Mekong River is not only a problem of Vietnam but of all six countries in the basin. I would like to close my research with a famous quote by F. Engels: "We cannot treat nature, dominating nature like an invader who dominates other peoples, as an outsider of nature. On the contrary, we belong to it with bones, flesh, blood and mind, and we are within it. Unlike other creatures, our total dominion over nature consists in being able to recognize its laws and apply them properly" (Quang, 2014, 111-112). The saying is a passionate advice of the ancestors for posterity. If all of us understand and follow the spirit of the above sentence, the image of a rich Mekong Delta region "on the wharf, under the boat, clear water, white rice" is not only in the subconscious but will forever exist forever.

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